

The Coupling Constant Series and the Conservation of Variation

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Abstract:

The following is an analysis of the coupling constant primordial function. in continuation to the proof of the first three interactions to be scalar multiples at $24 + 2$, Lorentz manifold variation, invoked stationary. One would argue for the existence of a new conservation law, the conservation of variation (net curvature) on the Lorentz manifold (M, g_E) with signature $(3,1)$. Such a conservation law comes to an agreement with the dynamic nature of the interactions and the fact they are scalar multiples on the connected manifold, which was invoked stationary $M = M_0 \times R$.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1}$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.1}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.11}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{2.1}$$

$$8 + (1) + 3 - (1v): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 3 \tag{2.1}$$

In the paper about the interactions dynamic nature, we varied the first and the third interactions, i.e. the strong and the electric, in their N_V element, so all the net variations will align on the same integer. The important point, which was not mentioned, is that the net variations varying their position among the terms are confined within the manifold. In other words, it is conserved. That is also the case with the gravitational coupling, which as far as the 8T can predict, is a result of two net variations added to the original net variation. The data regarding the nature of gravity came from the second representation, i.e. the spin representation of the coupling constant equation.

$$[2N(\text{gravity}) + 2] = \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} = [(2N(g)) + (3)] + N_{V1} + N_{V2} + N_{V3} \quad (2.2)$$

We can put the conservation law in rigor and construct an appropriate theorem:

Theorem (1.0) – The sum of net variations on all the coupling elements cannot escape the manifold.

Theorem (1.1): The sum of all net variations increase with time.

$$\oint_{t=0}^{t=Z} (dM)(M_0 \times R) \left(\sum_{V=0}^{\infty} N_V \right) \in M \quad (3)$$

$$Z \rightarrow \infty$$

If one constructed properly, one summation of the net variation to each V across the entire manifold matrix, over time, must belong to the manifold itself and cannot decrease. It could be related to the second rule of thermodynamic, the entropy rise alongside the net variations overtime. Of course, the total variations grow much faster, but that was not the subject of this paper. The point was to emphasize that the sum of net variation is bounded to the manifold, despite the fact it grows with time.

References

[1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)